

ВЕСТНИК

Харьковского
Регионального
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Проблем
Общественного
Здравоохранения

ВІСНИК
Харківського
Регіонального
Інституту
Проблем
Громадської
Охорони
Здоров'я

BULLETIN of
Kharkiv
Regional
Institute of
Public
Health
Services

ISSN 2707-9287

Харьковский Региональный Институт Проблем Общественного Здравоохранения.
Код ЕГРПОУ 26419943. Дата государственной регистрации: 01.08.2003.
Номер записи в ЕГРПОУ: 1 480 120 0000 001081. Дата записи: 01.09.2004.

Вестник Харьковского Регионального Института Проблем Общественного Здравоохранения

Издается с 2004 года. ISSN [2707-9287](#)

Год Номер

2004 - 1, 2
2005 - 3(1), 4(2), 5(3), 6(4), 7(5), 8(6)
2006 - 9(1), 10(2), 11(3), 12(4), 13(5), 14(6)
2007 - 15(1), 16(2), 17(3), 18(4), 19(5), 20(6)
2008 - 21(1), 22(2), 23(3), 24(4), 25(5), 26(6)
2009 - 27(1), 28(2), 29(3), 30(4), 31(5), 32(6)
2010 - 33(1), 34(2), 35(3), 36(4), 37(5), 38(6)
2011 - 39(1), 40(2), 41(3), 42(4), 43(5), 44(6)
2012 - 45(1), 46(2), 47(3), 48(4), 49(5), 50(6)
2013 - 51(1), 52(2), 53(3), 54(4), 55(5), 56(6)
2014 - 57(1), 58(2), 59(3), 60(4), 61(5), 62(6)
2015 - 63(1), 64(2), 65(3), 66(4), 67(5), 68(6)
2016 - 69(1), 70(2), 71(3), 72(4), 73(5), 74(6)
2017 - 75(1), 76(2), 77(3), 78(4), 79(5), 80(6)
2018 - 81(1), 82(2), 83(3), 84(4), 85(5), 86(6)
2019 - 87(1), 88(2), 89(3), 90(4), 91(5), 92(6)
2020 - 93(1), 94(2), 95(3), **96(4)**

Распространяется по подписке, бесплатно.

Языки публикаций: русский, украинский, английский, немецкий, французский, испанский.

Подписано в печать: 31.08.2020. Протокол № 4'2020/вестник.

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Вісник Харківського Регіонального Інституту Проблем Громадської Охорони Здоров'я

Видається з 2004 року. Розповсюджується безкоштовно.

Мови публікацій: російська, українська, англійська, німецька, французька, іспанська.

Bulletin of Kharkiv Regional Institute of Public Health Services or Bulletin of Kharkov Regional Institute of Public Health Services

Published since 2004. Distributed free of charge.

Languages of publications: Russian, Ukrainian, English, German, French, Spanish.

MEDICAL AND SOCIAL EVALUATION OF QUALITY OF LIFE OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES

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Into the section: Social medicine and healthcare management

Based on the results of original research, the levels of quality of life of different classification groups of children with disabilities in Kharkiv-city and Kharkiv region in terms of providing them with medical and social assistance were analyzed.

Keywords: quality of life, questionnaire, medical and social assistance, disability, child disability, restriction blocks.

Introduction. Child disability in almost all cases leads to social maladaptation through a number of disorders of the child: development and growth, ability to self-care, movement, orientation, and control over their behavior, learning, communication and work in the future [1–4]. Nevertheless, people with disabilities should have a level of physical, psychological, social and economic capabilities that will allow them to lead a full socio-economic and creative life mentally [5–7]. The latter is possible only with a full-fledged comprehensive analysis of the physical, psychological and social problems of the disabled child and taking into account the subjective assessment of the level of the above capabilities of both the child and his parents. This is achieved through a comprehensive integrated assessment of quality of life (QoL) [8–10], which combines components such as physical, mental, spiritual health, satisfaction with living conditions, medical and social security, etc.

The purpose of the study is to develop a basic methodology and assess the level of QoL of children with disabilities at the individual and population levels.

Materials and methods of research. The author's method of determining QoL is based on the use of WHO recommendations and requirements, which include the following blocks of restrictions: "restriction of physical activity", "psychological restrictions", "restrictions on the level of independence", "restrictions on the environment", "restrictions on spirituality", "restrictions social life" [11].

The study of QoL is based on the anamnestic OP of the closed type developed by the author, consisting of two parts. The first lists 30 daily restrictions that a disabled child may have. From these constraints she needs to choose the six most important for her, as well as additionally answer and evaluate another 42 standardized questions, which make it possible to identify a number of daily constraints, each of which is evaluated in points on a five-point scale and summarize into total level of restrictions (TLR) of a disabled child [12].

Quantitative assessment of the individual QoL index (IIQoL) of a disabled child is based on the TLR according to the author's formula and is expressed as a percentage [12]. Assessment of IIQoL at the individual and population levels was carried out according to the following scale of author's assessments: the optimal level — QoL is in the range from 100.0 % to 70.0 %; average level — from 31.0 % to 69.0 %; low level — 30.0 % and below.

Using the data filled in by children with disabilities, we created a database of studies of IIQoL, which compiled data on 521 physical units of observation (children with disabilities aged 0 to 18 years living in Kharkiv and the region). Further in-depth analysis of the obtained results consisted in the assessment of IIQoL of individual questionnaires of different groups (depending on age, gender, residence (city or village and home or specialized boarding school), severity of disabling pathology, QoL level).

When processing the material, relative and average values, prognostic coefficients were calculated. Regression (simple, multiple), correlation analyzes were used; methods of mathematical forecasting and modeling, method of system approach and analysis, structural-logical and others. We have taken into account the recommendations on the use of statistical methods in the performance of socio-hygienic research (A. S. Polyakov, A. M. Merkov, 1974, E. N. Shigan, 1986, 1987, M. B. Slavin, 1989, G. F. Lakin, 1990, C. Glanz, 1999, A. P. Kulaichev, 1998, S. P. Lapach, A. V. Chubenko, P. N. Babych, 2000, etc.). Evaluation of the data was performed on IBM-Pentium IV using the application package "Stadia-6" (serial number of the license passport 1218 from May 24, 2000, version "Prof"), Microsoft "Access", "Excel".

Research results and discussion. According to our research, the QoL of children with disabilities in Kharkiv and the region averages 64.33 % (from 23.44 % to 85.42 %).

In an in-depth analysis of QoL levels, we obtained the following data: 3 children had a low QoL level (0.58 %), 352 children had a medium QoL level (67.56 %), and 166 children had an optimal QoL level (31.86 %) (Table 1).

Table 1

Quality of life of children with disabilities depending on gender, age, residence and severity of disability, %

No.	Groups of children	Level of QoL			Total
		Low	Medium	Optimal	
1	Boys	2 (66,67%)	222 (63,07%)	92 (55,42%)	316 (60,65%)
2	Girls	1 (33,33%)	130 (36,93%)	74 (44,58%)	205 (39,35%)
3	Children 0 – 10 years	2 (66,67%)	121 (34,38%)	46 (27,72%)	169 (32,43%)
4	Children 11 – 14 years	1 (33,33%)	145 (41,19%)	64 (38,55%)	210 (40,31%)
5	Children 15 – 18 years	-	86 (24,43%)	56 (33,73%)	142 (27,26%)
6	Children from rural places	-	184 (52,27%)	76 (45,78%)	260 (49,90%)
7	Children from cities	3 (100,00%)	168 (47,73%)	90 (54,22%)	261 (50,10%)
8	Children from special schools	-	95 (26,99%)	21 (12,65%)	116 (22,26%)
9	Children from homes	3 (100,00%)	257 (73,01%)	145 (87,35%)	405 (77,74%)
10	Low grade	-	42 (11,93%)	25 (15,06%)	67 (12,86%)
11	Medium grade	2 (66,67%)	213 (60,51%)	133 (80,12%)	348 (66,79%)
12	High grade	1 (33,33%)	97 (27,56%)	8 (4,82%)	106 (20,35%)
13	Total	3 (0,58%)	352 (67,56%)	166 (31,86%)	521 (100%)

After analyzing in more detail the levels of QoL of groups of children with disabilities (depending on age, gender, residence (city or village and home or specialized boarding school), the severity of the disabling pathology), we found the following patterns:

1) the majority of children with an average level of QoL are boys (63.07 % and 36.93 % girls, respectively); are children aged 11–14 and 0–10 years, than 15–18 (41.19 %, 34.38 % and 24.43 % respectively). The maximum number of these children lives at home (73.01 %) and has a moderate (60.51 %) and severe (27.56 %) degree of disability;

2) in the group of children with the optimal level of QoL, there are mostly boys than girls (55.42 % and 44.58 %, respectively); the number of children is higher at the age of 11–14 (38.55 %) and 15–18 years (33.73 %); most live at home (87.35 %) and have moderate (80.12 %) and mild (15.06 %) degrees of disability.

In addition to the above, we conducted a more detailed analysis of QoL in general, depending on gender, age, place of residence of children and the severity of disability. It was found that the degree of severity of disability has a significant impact on QoL. According to our research, in children with a mild severity QoL is on average 68.87 % (from 52.08 % to 83.85 %), then with a moderate degree — 65.97 % (23.44 %–85.41 %), and in severe — 56.11 % (29.17 %–80.21 %) — table. 2.

Table 2

Dependence of mean QoL of children with disabilities on severity of disability, gender, age and place of residence (%)

No.	Groups	Grade of disability			Total
		Low	Medium	High	
1	Boys	68,29%	65,09%	56,73%	63,65%
2	Girls	69,77%	67,22%	54,90%	65,38%
3	Children 0 – 10 years	66,20%	65,98%	53,19%	63,11%
4	Children 11 – 14 years	68,13%	65,56%	56,33%	64,37%
5	Children 15 – 18 years	72,57%	66,49%	59,63%	65,73%
6	Children from rural places	67,68%	65,45%	55,54%	63,86%
7	Children from cities	70,85%	64,45%	56,64%	64,80%
8	Children from special schools	66,92%	63,72%	65,10%	65,12%
9	Children from homes	73,14%	66,43%	55,07%	64,11%
	Total	68,87%	65,97%	56,11%	64,33%

In the analysis of the influence of the severity of the disabling pathology, we found:

1) depending on the gender, age, place of residence of children with mild severity of disability: in children 14–18 years QoL is higher than in children 11–14 and 0–10 years (72.57 %, 68.13 % and 66.20 % respectively); There is also a significant discrepancy in the indicators of QoL of children living at home and in boarding schools (73.14 % and 66.92 % respectively);

2) in children with severe disability, we found quite significant differences in the levels of QoL in children living in boarding schools and at home (65.10 % and 55.07 %, respectively);

In order to determine the influence of individual blocks of restrictions on the QoL of children with disabilities, we built and analyzed a correlation matrix (Table 3) and a mathematical model of QoL of these children.

Table 3

Correlation matrix of dependence of blocks of everyday limitations and QoL of children with disabilities

	Physical limitations	Psychological, social and spiritual limitations	Environmental limitations	Autonomy limitations	QoL
Physical limitations	1	0,37	0,31	0,54	0,69
Psychological, social and spiritual limitations	0,37	1	0,57	0,52	0,84
Environmental limitations	0,31	0,57	1	0,51	0,76
Autonomy limitations	0,54	0,52	0,51	1	0,84
QoL	0,69	0,81	0,76	0,84	1

It was found that the most significant impact on QoL in children with disabilities has a block of psychological limitations, limitations of social life and spirituality (0.84 — correlation matrix, $R_{xy} = -7.56$ — multiple linear regression), second place is held by the limitations in levels of independence (0.84 — correlation matrix, $R_{xy} = -6.5$ — multiple linear regression), then environmental constraints (0.76 — correlation matrix, $R_{xy} = -5.59$ — multiple linear regression), and physical constraints 0.69 — correlation matrix, $R_{xy} = -5.32$ — multiple linear regression).

Based on this, the interaction of all the above factors with each other has a complex effect on QoL. The total influence of the blocks of these factors is 99.88 % of all existing restrictions in these children (the coefficient of determination is 99.88 %). However, according to our research, we do not cover only 0.12 % of other factors that may also provide restrictions on the daily activities of this cohort of children, but in our opinion, these factors are not able to affect the QoL significantly. Based on the above, the model developed by us has a high degree of informativeness.

In addition to the mathematical model, we compiled and analyzed the prognostic matrix of QoL of children with disabilities in order to be able to predict it further with any change in the components that affect the QoL (Table 4).

First, we changed one block that affects the QoL, then two, three and four (1 group). Thus, if a child with a disability worsens the environment (3 block) 2 times, the QoL will deteriorate relative to baseline in 0.93 times (4 option), with increasing restrictions on the level of independence in 2 times (4 block) QoL will deteriorate in 0.91 (5 option).

Table 4

Prognosis matrix of dependence of QoL of children with disabilities on everyday limitations

Number of changed blocks (groups)	Types	Blocks of limitations (factors)				Level of QoL (R _{xy})	Change of QoL, times
		1-block	2-block	3-block	4-block		
1	1	x1=1	x2=1	x3=1	x4=1	Y=74,9	1,00
	2	x1=2	x2=1	x3=1	x4=1	Y=69,6	0,93
	3	x1=1	x2=2	x3=1	x4=1	Y=67,4	0,90
	4	x1=1	x2=1	x3=2	x4=1	Y=69,3	0,93
	5	x1=1	x2=1	x3=1	x4=2	Y=68,4	0,91
2	6	x1=2	x2=2	x3=1	x4=1	Y=62	0,83
	7	x1=2	x2=1	x3=2	x4=1	Y=64	0,85
	8	x1=2	x2=1	x3=1	x4=2	Y=63,1	0,84
	9	x1=1	x2=2	x3=2	x4=1	Y=61,8	0,83
	10	x1=1	x2=2	x3=1	x4=2	Y=63,4	0,85
	11	x1=1	x2=1	x3=2	x4=2	Y=62,8	0,84
3	12	x1=2	x2=2	x3=2	x4=1	Y=56,4	0,75
	13	x1=2	x2=2	x3=1	x4=2	Y=55,5	0,74
	14	x1=2	x2=1	x3=2	x4=2	Y=57,5	0,77
	15	x1=1	x2=2	x3=2	x4=2	Y=55,3	0,74
4	16	x1=2	x2=2	x3=2	x4=2	Y=50	0,67

At the same time at simultaneous increase in restrictions of level of independence and deterioration of environmental conditions in 2 times, the level of QoL will worsen in 0,84 times (11 option), and at deterioration of all blocks of restrictions in 2 times, the QoL level will worsen in 0,67 times (16 option), etc.

The conducted forecasting has great prognostic possibilities and plays a significant role in the development of programs to improve living conditions, increase the level of viability and social integration of children with disabilities in society; justification of medical and social measures aimed at maintaining the maximum level of health of these children, improving their living conditions in the environment, etc.

Conclusions. Based on the above, we are able to draw the following conclusions:

1. in general, the rate of QoL of children with disabilities is 64.33 % and ranges from 23.44 % to 85.42 %. At the same time, 0.58 % of the studied children have a low level of QoL, an average level of 67.56 %, and an optimal level of 31.86 %. Of these children, the average level of QoL is the majority of boys (63.07 %); children aged 11–14 and 0–10 years (41.19 % and 34.38 % respectively); children living at home (73.01 %) and having moderate (60.51 %) and severe (27.56 %) degrees of disability. At the same time, among boys with the optimal level of QoL most boys (55.42 %); children aged 11–14 (38.55 %) and 15–18 years (33.73 %); children living at home (87.35 %) and having a moderate (80.12 %) and mild (15.06 %) severity of disability;

2. the level of severity of disability has the maximum influence on the level of QoL (in children with a mild severity of QoL 68.87 %, with moderate — 65.97 %, with severe — 56.11 %). Of these groups of children, with a mild degree of disability, QoL is higher in children aged 14–18 (72.57 %) and in children living at home (73.14 %). In children with severe disability, QoL is higher in those living in boarding schools (65.10 %);

3. among the limitations that have the greatest impact on QoL in children with disabilities are a block of psychological limitations together with the limitations of social life and spirituality; restrictions on the level of independence; restrictions caused by the external environment and restrictions on physical activity. In total, they are 99.88 %. The most important of them are the block of psychological restrictions together with the restrictions of social life and spirituality (34.32 %) and the block of restrictions in the level of independence (27.54 %).

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Cite as: [Mishchenko AN. Medical and social evaluation of quality of life of children with disabilities. Bull KhRIPHS (ISSN 2707-9279; Kharkiv), 2020;96(4):41-47. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4905883>]

Для цитирования, на русском: [Мищенко АН. Медико-социальная оценка качества жизни детей-инвалидов. Вестник ХРИПОЗ (ISSN 2707-9279; Харьков), 2020;96(4):41-47. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4905883> (Англ.)]

По результатам оригинального исследования проанализированы уровни качества жизни различных классификационных групп детей-инвалидов Харькова и Харьковской области в части оказания им медико-социальной помощи.

Ключевые слова: качество жизни, анкета, медико-социальная помощь, инвалидность, детская инвалидность, ограничительные блоки.

Для цитування, українською мовою: [Мищенко ОМ. Медико-соціальна оцінка якості життя дітей-інвалідів. Вісник ХРИПОЗ (ISSN 2707-9279; Харків), 2020;96(4):41-47. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4905883> (Англ.)]

За результатами оригінальних досліджень проаналізовано рівні якості життя різних класифікаційних груп дітей-інвалідів Харкова та Харківської області з точки зору надання їм медичної та соціальної допомоги.

Ключові слова: якість життя, анкета, медична та соціальна допомога, інвалідність, дитяча інвалідність, обмежувальні блоки.

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Received: May 04, 2020.

Published: August 12, 2020.